

Cracking The Code of The Third Root : A Non-surgical Strategy For Radix Entomolaris

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Abstract

Radix entomolaris (RE) is a rare anatomical variation characterized by a supernumerary distolingual root in mandibular molars. Its presence complicates endodontic treatment due to increased chances of missed canals and altered morphology. This case report presents the successful nonsurgical management of a mandibular first molar with RE and a large periapical lesion. Through precise diagnosis, modified access design, calcium hydroxide dressings, and use of bioceramic sealer, complete healing was achieved without surgical intervention. Early detection and a biologically guided protocol are key to managing such anatomical complexities.

Introduction

The true outcome of endodontic treatment ultimately depends on the capacity to locate, cleanse and obturate the entire root canal system. Nonetheless, anatomic anomalies, such as existence of an additional root, radix entomolaris (RE), present a great difficulty in mandibular molars. RE is the presence of a supernumerary distolingual root and most frequently observed in the mandibular first molar. Although less frequent in Caucasians and Indians (incidence <5%)^{1,2}, its detection is necessary to prevent endodontic failure secondary to untreated canals. First described by Carabelli, RE calls for practitioners to modify and tailor both diagnostic and treatment regimens, especially with respect to access cavity morphology and contact-point exploration.^{1,3}

When RE is linked to periapical pathology - such as granulomas, cysts, or abscesses - which frequently arises from a chronic bacterial infection of the pulp and root canal system, the complexity is increased.⁴ Non surgical endodontic therapy is still the first-line treatment for periapical lesions, which can range in size from tiny radiolucencies to massive cystic entities.⁵ When appropriate nonsurgical protocols are used, such as adequate chemomechanical debridement, intracanal medications like calcium hydroxide, and long-term follow-up, studies have shown

success rates as high as 85–94%.⁶⁻⁸

Due to changed canal morphology, negotiation challenges, and the possibility of missed anatomy, the presence of RE makes nonsurgical management of such lesions more difficult. However, even complex cases can be resolved conservatively with biological approaches to periapical healing combined with careful diagnostic tools like CBCT imaging, angled radiographs, and magnification.^{1,2,9}

The management of a mandibular first molar with radix entomolaris and a large periapical lesion is demonstrated in this case study, highlighting the importance of accurate diagnosis and biologically oriented endodontic procedures in achieving full healing without the need for surgery.

Case Report

Case Report

A 21-year-old female patient, Shahin, reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College, Ghaziabad, with a chief complaint of severe pain in the lower left back tooth region for the past five days.

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The pain was intermittent, exacerbated by the intake of hot food and beverages, and persisted for 2-3 hours. Clinical examination revealed deep proximal caries in the left mandibular first molar, with otherwise satisfactory oral hygiene. A preoperative radiograph showed a radiolucency involving enamel and dentin, approaching the pulp, along with the presence of an additional distolingual root - confirming the diagnosis of Radix Entomolaris. A periapical radiolucency was also evident around both the distal and mesial roots, indicating periapical pathology.

Figure 1 : Preoperative radiograph

Treatment Procedure

Access Cavity Preparation : Local anesthesia was administered, and rubber dam isolation was achieved. Access cavity was modified to a trapezoidal shape to locate all canals, including the distolingual root canal (RE). Canal orifices were identified using a DG-16 explorer.

Working Length Determination : Patency was established using a #10 K-file. Working length was determined using an apex locator and confirmed radiographically (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Working Length Determination

The root canals were instrumented using K-files to create a glide path for the rotary instrumentation. Cleaning and shaping were performed using endostar rotary files upto 25/06 in each canal. During cleaning and shaping, the root canals were irrigated with copious amounts of 2.5% sodium hypochlorite solution (UPS Hygienes Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, Maharashtra, India). The canals were then rinsed with EDTA (DeSmear, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India).

Saline was used for the final rinse of the canals and dried using paper points.

After thorough cleaning and shaping of all canals— A creamy paste of calcium hydroxide was placed in all canals using a Lentulo spiral.

The access cavity was sealed temporarily with Cavit-G. The patient was recalled after 7 days.

Second Appointment : After 7 days the temporary restoration was removed, and the canals were irrigated with normal saline and NaOCl to remove the previous dressing. Fresh calcium hydroxide was reapplied in the canals. The patient was asymptomatic and scheduled for the next recall in 10 days.

Third appointment : After The dressing was removed again with copious irrigation using NaOCl and EDTA. Calcium hydroxide was reapplied for the third and final time. The patient showed clinical signs of improvement and radiographic signs of initial healing. The patient was recalled after 7 days.

Following three cycles of intracanal medication over approximately 3 weeks, the periapical lesion had begun to regress radiographically, and the patient remained asymptomatic.

The master cone was selected and confirmed radiographically. (Figure 3)

Figure 3: Master Cone

Obturation was done using single cone technique with gutta-percha and bioceramic sealer sealer.

The quality of obturation was confirmed with a final radiograph. (figure : 4)

Figure 4 : Obturation

Discussion

In mandibular molars, the supernumerary distolingual root known as Radix entomolaris (RE) presents a notable anatomical variation that, if not correctly identified, may jeopardize endodontic results. The prevalence of RE is considerably higher (5–30%) in populations with Mongoloid traits, such as Chinese, Eskimos, and Native Americans, but it is comparatively low (<5%) in Indian and Caucasian populations. Additionally, more than 50% of cases have been reported to have bilateral occurrence, highlighting the significance of assessing the contralateral molar when one RE is found.^{1,2,3,10}

The intricacy of RE in clinical practice is due to its additional canal as well as its morphological variations and curvature, which frequently make access, cleaning, and shaping more difficult. Classification schemes like Carlsen and Alexandersen's (based on cervical location) and De Moor et al.'s (based on root curvature) offer a helpful framework to predict the canal's course and direct the clinician's approach.^{1,11} With cervical positioning that varies between distal, mesial, or central orientations, RE can present as straight (Type I), coronal-curved (Type II), or double-curved (Type III).

Accurate diagnosis through multiple angulated radiographs or CBCT imaging is essential to avoid missing this extra root. In this case, modifying the access cavity to a trapezoidal form was crucial in locating the RE canal, consistent with established recommendations. The canal was successfully negotiated using small hand files and prepared with rotary instruments. The use of sodium hypochlorite, EDTA, and calcium hydroxide as intracanal medicament over three appointments facilitated effective disinfection and promoted healing of the associated periapical lesion. Ultimately, obturation with bioceramic sealer and gutta-percha ensured a hermetic seal in the complex canal morphology.^{2,4,9}

This case emphasizes how crucial it is to comprehend the anatomical variations of root canals and use a step-by-step, biologically oriented protocol to manage RE. Even complex cases like RE can be successfully managed conservatively with careful chemomechanical preparation, access modification, and appropriate diagnosis.

Conclusion

This case shows that even though radix entomolaris is uncommon, it can be effectively treated with careful canal instrumentation, a modified access preparation, and an accurate diagnosis. The related periapical lesion was able to heal without surgery thanks to the application of calcium hydroxide dressings over several visits. When done precisely and with biological consideration, conservative endodontic therapy is still effective for complex anatomical variations.

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